

Rac-7c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-1-rac-20%-IF	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	106	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 153 1 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	256.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 256.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/26/2022 8:09:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/26/2022 8:40:30 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.662	3176039	49.94	323927
2	8.347	3184283	50.06	293145

Asy-7c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-1-ASY-20%-IF	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	8	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 153 1 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	256.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 256.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/26/2022 8:25:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/26/2022 8:43:15 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.648	15375436	95.85	1571984
2	8.350	665052	4.15	66029